

THYROID FUNCTION ABNORMALITIES IN PATIENTS WITH TYPE II DIABETES MELLITUS

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Abstract

Objective: To assess the thyroid function abnormalities in patients with type II diabetes Mellitus.

Study design: Cross sectional study

Place and duration of study: Department of Chemical Pathology, Bahawal Victoria Hospital, Bahawalpur for duration 6 months from 8th May, 2024 to 8th November 2024.

Methodology: One hundred and fifteen patients were enrolled and blood sample was taken for assessment of thyroid function test. Reports were assessed and levels of thyroid function test were recorded. The data was collected in Performa while later on analysed with SPSS v. 25.0. Thyroid function tests (TSH, T3, T4) were presented by mean +/- SD.

Results: In this study, we enrolled with the mean age of 50.00 ± 12.23 years. There were 60 (52.2%) male diabetic patients and 55 (47.8%) female diabetic patients. Laboratory findings of thyroid function tests were as follows: mean TSH level was 3.30 ± 1.79 mIU/L, mean T3 level was 118.34 ± 38.31 ng/dL and mean T4 level was 7.94 ± 1.85 µg/dL. Out of 115 diabetic patients, 22 (19.13%) had thyroid function abnormality.

Conclusion: Although the frequency of thyroid function abnormality is less than 20%, but cannot be ignored as it can deteriorate the quality of life of diabetic patients.

INTRODUCTION

Diabetes is a global pandemic. Globally, the prevalence of diabetes has increased as a result of the rise in obesity and lifestyle changes.^{1,2} Type II diabetes mellitus (T2DM) and thyroid dysfunction (TD) are common endocrine disorders usually encountered in clinical practice.^{3,4} Diabetes and thyroid disorders have

been shown to mutually influence each other, and association between both conditions has long been reported.^{5,6} The prevalence (6.6%) of thyroid disease is common in the general population and increases with age. The prevalence of thyroid disease in diabetes has been estimated at 10.8%, with the majority of cases

occurring as hypothyroidism (~30%) and subclinical hypothyroidism (~50%). Hyperthyroidism accounts for 12% and postpartum thyroiditis accounts for 11%.^{6,7}

Diabetes and thyroid diseases are caused by endocrine dysfunction and both have been demonstrated to mutually impact each other.^{5,6}

In Pakistan, thyroid function abnormalities can be observed to be 9% among patients of type II diabetes mellitus.⁸ Several studies have shown a higher prevalence of thyroid disorders in patients with diabetes mellitus and vice versa. Thyroid hormone affects glucose homeostasis by impacting pancreatic β -cell development and glucose metabolism through several organs such as the liver, gastrointestinal tract, pancreas, adipose tissue, skeletal muscles, and the central nervous system.⁹

Aim of this study is to assess the thyroid function abnormalities in patients with type II diabetes Mellitus. Literature showed that the levels of thyroid function tests significant deranged among diabetics than non-diabetics. But conflicting data has been observed in literature, showing insignificant relationship and limited work has been done in this regard. Also no local study had been done before in this regard. Therefore, there is a need to conduct a study in local setting to confirm whether levels are deranged or lies within normal limits. So, we want to conduct this study to get evidence for local population and in future we will implement a practice to screen diabetic patients on regular intervals for thyroid function tests in order to timely detect any changes in thyroid function.

METHODOLOGY:

This Cross-sectional study was conducted at the Department of Chemical Pathology, Bahawal Victoria Hospital, Bahawalpur for duration of 6 months from 8th May, 2024 to 8th November 2024. By using WHO calculator, sample size of 115 cases is calculated with 95% confidence level, $d=0.25$ and mean TSH level i.e. 1.52 ± 1.27 μ IU/ml in diabetic patients.¹⁰ All the patients were enrolled by using non-probability, consecutive sampling technique who fulfilled following criteria:

Inclusion: Patients having age 30-70 years, both gender, diagnosed with type II diabetes mellitus were enrolled. Diabetes was defined as presence of HbA1c >5.5% for >1 year and patient is taking anti-glycemic medication.¹⁰

Exclusion: Patients with chronic liver disease (cirrhosis, hepatitis B or C), diabetes mellitus type I, history of thyroid surgeries, chronic hypothyroidism (TSH >5IU) before diabetes, chronic renal failure (serum creatinine >1.8 mg/dl or on dialysis) were excluded from the study.

All the patients were enrolled from outpatient department. Informed written consent was taken from patients. Demographic history including age, gender, BMI, duration of diabetes, residence, HbA1c, history of smoking, alcoholism, dyslipidemia, hypertension, and f/h thyroid disease were recorded. Then blood sample was taken in a 5cc disposable syringe by a staff nurse under supervision of researcher by following aseptic measures. All the samples were stored carefully in sterile vials containing anti-coagulation material and were sent to the laboratory of the hospital for assessment of thyroid function test. Reports were assessed and levels of thyroid function test were recorded. TSH: It was assessed in terms of mIU/L. Normal range: 0.5 to 5.0 mIU/L. T3: It was assessed in terms of ng/dL. Normal range: 80-220 ng/dL. T4: It was assessed in terms of μ g/dL. Normal range: 5.0 to 12.0 μ g/dL. Patients with deranged thyroid function test were managed as per standard protocol. The data was collected in Performa.

The data was analyzed with SPSS v. 25.0. Thyroid function tests (TSH, T3, T4) were presented by mean \pm SD. Effect modifiers like age, gender, BMI, duration of diabetes, residence, HbA1c, history of smoking, alcoholism, dyslipidemia, hypertension, and f/h thyroid disease were controlled by stratification. Post-stratification, independent samples t-test was applied to compare thyroid function tests in stratified groups. P value ≤ 0.05 was kept as significant.

RESULTS

In this study, we enrolled with the mean age of 50.00 ± 12.23 years. There were 60 (52.2%) male diabetic patients and 55 (47.8%) female diabetic patients. The mean BMI of patients was 25.38 ± 5.81 kg/m². Mostly patients (71.3%) were residing in urban areas. There were 37 (32.2%) smokers, 13 (11.3%) were alcoholic, 58 (50.4%) had history of hypertension, 61 (53.0%) had dyslipidemia and 52 (45.2%) had family history of thyroid dysfunction. Less than 50% patients were taking insulin with or without oral antiglycemic drugs. Table I

Laboratory findings of thyroid function tests were as follows: mean TSH level was 3.30 ± 1.79 mIU/L, mean T3 level was 118.34 ± 38.31 ng/dL and mean T4 level was 7.94 ± 1.85 µg/dL. Table II

Out of 115 diabetic patients, 22 (19.13%) had thyroid function abnormality. Fig I

Mean level of thyroid function test were compared in different age, gender, BMI, and other effect modifiers groups. It has been observed that age had no impact on TSH and T4 level but T3 was significantly high in patients 30-50 years old. TSH was significantly higher in males as compared to females, but T4 level was less among males (p<0.05). But T3 level was insignificant (p>0.05). BMI, and duration of diabetes have no impact on deranged thyroid function test level (P>0.05). In patients with uncontrolled diabetes, T4 level was significantly lower than patients with controlled diabetes, while TSH and T3 level were insignificantly higher in patients with controlled diabetes

(p>0.05). Smoking has significant effect on T4 level (p<0.05), but alcoholism, dyslipidemia, hypertension and family history of thyroid dysfunction have no relationship with thyroid function test levels (p>0.05). Residence has also no significant relationship with thyroid function test levels (p>0.05). Patients taking insulin only and oral anti-glycemic only has significantly increased TSH level as compared to patients taking combination drugs, either with or without insulin (p<0.05). Patients taking insulin has significantly increased T4 level as compared to patients taking oral anti-glycemic drugs (p<0.05). Patients taking insulin only has no significant impact on increased T3 level as compared to patients taking oral anti-glycemic drugs (p>0.05). Table II

Comparison of Thyroid function abnormality in different age, gender, BMI and other effect modifiers groups was assessed. It has been observed that age has no impact on abnormal thyroid function, while males were more prone to abnormal thyroid function as compared to females (30% vs. 7.30%, p-value = 0.002). BMI, duration of diabetes, glycemic control, alcoholism, dyslipidemia, hypertension, family history of thyroid dysfunction, and residence have no association with abnormal thyroid function (p>0.05). But among smokers, thyroid function abnormality was significantly higher (29.7%) as compared to non-smokers (14.1%, p<0.05). Thyroid function abnormality was more common with insulin use only (51.6%), while nil in patients taking combination drugs or when prescribed with insulin (p<0.05). Table III

Table I: Demographics characteristics of diabetic patients enrolled in the study (n = 115)

Age (years)	50.00 ± 12.23
Gender	
Male	60 (52.2%)
Female	55 (47.8%)
BMI (kg/m ²)	25.38 ± 5.81
Residence	
Rural	33 (28.7%)
Urban	82 (71.3%)
History of	
Smoking	37 (32.2%)
Alcoholism	13 (11.3%)

Hypertension	58 (50.4%)
Dyslipidemia	61 (53.0%)
Family history of thyroid dysfunction	52 (45.2%)
Duration of Diabetes (years)	8.61 ± 6.92
HbA1c (%)	8.10 ± 0.91
Treatment taking for diabetes	
Insulin only	31 (27.0%)
Oral anti-glycemic	30 (26.1%)
Combination of oral drugs	34 (29.6%)
Insulin with oral antiglycemic	20 (17.4%)

Table II: Laboratory findings of thyroid function tests (n = 115)

	Mean ± SD, F (%)
TSH (mIU/L)	3.30 ± 1.79
T3 level (ng/dL)	118.34 ± 38.31
T4 level (µg/dL)	7.94 ± 1.85

Fig I: Thyroid function abnormality

Table II: Mean Thyroid function tests level in patients divided in different age, gender, BMI, and other effect modifiers groups

		n	TSH	T3	T4
Age (in years)	30-50	61	3.10 ± 1.75	125.21 ± 38.86	7.82 ± 1.81
	51-70	54	3.53 ± 1.82	110.57 ± 36.48	8.08 ± 1.91
p-value			0.203	0.040	0.455
Gender	Male	60	3.80 ± 1.88	122.60 ± 36.90	7.36 ± 1.90
	Female	55	2.76 ± 1.52	113.69 ± 39.60	8.58 ± 1.59
p-value			0.002	0.214	0.000
BMI	Underweight	17	3.10 ± 1.90	111.29 ± 31.56	8.22 ± 2.00
	Normal BMI	42	3.25 ± 1.62	127.60 ± 39.15	7.71 ± 1.99
	Overweight	29	3.00 ± 1.49	110.03 ± 40.06	8.23 ± 1.57
	Obese	27	3.83 ± 2.20	117.30 ± 37.77	7.82 ± 1.85
p-value			0.332	0.221	0.607
Duration of diabetes	1-5 years	55	3.10 ± 1.60	125.15 ± 38.74	7.73 ± 1.74
	6-10 years	22	3.78 ± 2.33	118.00 ± 39.16	8.00 ± 2.20
	>10 years	38	3.32 ± 1.68	108.68 ± 36.00	8.20 ± 1.81
p-value			0.319	0.125	0.488
HbA1c group	Controlled	73	3.37 ± 1.79	120.01 ± 39.53	8.28±2.13
	Uncontrolled	42	3.19 ± 1.80	115.43 ± 36.35	7.35±1.01
p-value			0.617	0.539	0.009
Smoking	Yes	37	3.71 ± 1.95	118.78 ± 35.75	7.36±1.98

	No	78	3.11 ± 1.69	118.13 ± 39.68	8.21±1.74
p-value			0.095	0.932	0.021
Alcoholic	Yes	13	3.93 ± 2.10	121.77 ± 35.72	7.38±1.87
	No	102	3.22 ± 1.74	117.90 ± 38.77	8.01±1.85
p-value			0.181	0.733	0.246
Dyslipidemia	Yes	61	3.36 ± 1.70	119.97 ± 40.27	7.94±1.68
	No	54	3.24 ± 1.90	116.50 ± 36.25	7.94±2.05
p-value			0.733	0.630	0.981
Hypertension	Yes	58	3.18 ± 1.70	120.12 ± 39.93	8.01±1.82
	No	57	3.43 ± 1.88	116.53 ± 36.95	7.86±1.89
p-value			0.449	0.617	0.668
Family history of thyroid dysfunction	Yes	52	3.49 ± 1.80	120.69 ± 39.87	7.83±1.69
	No	63	3.15 ± 1.78	116.40 ± 37.18	8.03±1.98
p-value			0.311	0.552	0.554
Residence	Rural	33	2.88 ± 1.57	112.91 ± 38.32	7.66±1.96
	Urban	82	3.47 ± 1.85	120.52 ± 38.31	8.05±1.81
p-value			0.109	0.337	0.307
Treatment of diabetes	Insulin only	31	4.39 ± 2.02	122.77 ± 36.94	8.34±2.76
	Oral anti-glycemic	30	3.05 ± 2.13	118.97 ± 41.51	6.45±0.88
	Combination of oral drugs	34	2.85 ± 1.18	119.56 ± 37.23	7.98±0.73
	Insulin with oral anti-glycemic	20	2.78 ± 0.87	108.45 ± 38.38	9.49±0.47
p-value			0.001	0.622	0.000

Table III: Comparison of Thyroid function abnormality in different age, gender, BMI and other effect modifiers groups.

		Thyroid function abnormality		P-value
		Yes (n = 22)	No (n=93)	
Age (in years)	30-50	11(18%)	50(82%)	0.75
	51-70	11(20.40%)	43(79.60%)	
Gender	Male	18(30%)	42(70%)	0.002
	Female	4(7.30%)	51(92.70%)	
BMI	Underweight	3(17.60%)	14(82.40%)	0.335
	Normal BMI	8(19%)	34(81%)	
	Overweight	3(10.30%)	26(89.70%)	
	Obese	8(29.60%)	19(70.40%)	
Duration of diabetes	1-5 years	9(16.40%)	46(83.60%)	0.068
	6-10 years	8(36.40%)	14(63.60%)	
	>10 years	5(13.20%)	33(86.80%)	
HbA1c	Controlled	17(23.30%)	56(76.70%)	0.135
	Uncontrolled	5(11.90%)	37(88.10%)	
Smoking	Yes	11(29.70%)	26(70.30%)	0.047
	No	11(14.10%)	67(85.90%)	
Alcoholic	Yes	4(30.80%)	9(69.20%)	0.257
	No	18(17.60%)	84(82.40%)	
Dyslipidemia	Yes	12(19.70%)	49(80.30%)	0.857
	No	10(18.50%)	44(81.50%)	

Hypertension	Yes	9(15.50%)	49(84.50%)	0.320
	No	13(22.80%)	44(77.20%)	
Family history of thyroid dysfunction	Yes	11(21.20%)	41(78.80%)	0.616
	No	11(17.50%)	52(82.50%)	
Residence	Rural	5(15.20%)	28(84.80%)	0.491
	Urban	17(20.70%)	65(79.30%)	
Treatment taking for diabetes	Insulin only	16(51.60%)	15(48.40%)	0.000
	Oral anti-glycemic	6(20%)	24(80%)	
	Combination of oral drugs	0(0%)	34(100%)	
	Insulin with oral anti-glycemic	0(0%)	20(100%)	

DISCUSSION

In our study, we observed that according to the laboratory findings, following levels of thyroid function test were obtained i.e. mean TSH level was 3.30 ± 1.79 mIU/L, mean T3 level was 118.34 ± 38.31 ng/dL and mean T4 level was 7.94 ± 1.85 µg/dL. Out of 115 diabetic patients, 22 (19.13%) had thyroid function abnormality. Thyroid dysfunction and diabetes mellitus are closely linked. Several studies have documented the increased prevalence of thyroid disorders in patients with diabetes mellitus and vice versa.¹¹

One study found that mean T3 level among diabetics was 2.22 ± 0.44 pg/dl that was not significant than controls (2.17 ± 0.45 pg/dl), mean T4 level was also almost similar among diabetics (1.05 ± 0.23 ng/dl) than controls (1.06 ± 0.30 ng/dl) but mean TSH level was also insignificant among diabetics (1.52 ± 1.27 µIU/ml) than controls (1.24 ± 0.84 µIU/ml).¹⁰ A study conducted in Quetta, it was reported that out of 224 diabetic patients, thyroid abnormalities were seen in 32.15% cases. The female population (58.93%) had higher risk of developing thyroid abnormality as compared to males.¹² In our study, we observed that males were at more risk of developing abnormal thyroid function as compared to females (30% vs. 7.30%, p-value = 0.002).

Both diabetes and thyroid dysfunction are chronic diseases that require lifelong treatment and have a long-lasting effect on cardiovascular health.³ As per a large European meta-analysis, thyroid dysfunction is present in 3.82% of the general population.¹³ Its prevalence among

diabetic patients is significantly higher, ranging from 9.9 to 48%.^{14, 15} This wide range of prevalence can be explained by the use of different definitions for thyroid dysfunction diagnosis, depending on the presence of anti-thyroid peroxidase (anti-TPO), antithyroglobulin antibody (anti-TG), or both. In many studies, most diabetic patients with thyroid dysfunction had subclinical hypothyroidism, and several new cases of thyroid dysfunction were diagnosed during clinical evaluations, highlighting the need for enhanced screening for thyroid dysfunction in diabetic patients.^{14, 16} Just as in the nondiabetic population, thyroid dysfunction was found to be more common in females than in males with diabetes.^{17, 18}

When the prevalence of thyroid dysfunction in patients with diabetes is examined, patients with type 1 and type 2 diabetes should be treated separately. Patients with type 1 diabetes are well-known to have an increased risk of developing other autoimmune disorders, including autoimmune thyroid disease.^{19, 20} The prevalence of thyroid dysfunction has been widely reported to be high in patients with type 2 diabetes, but others argue that the incidence of thyroid dysfunction is not dissimilar to that of the general population.^{21, 22} Thyroid hormones have a wide variety of physiological actions, some of which affect glucose metabolism. These actions include stimulation of general metabolism, absorption of glucose from the gut, and lipolysis. Poorly managed diabetes mellitus can lead to insulin resistance and hyperinsulinaemia, which causes thyroid tissue proliferation and increases

nodule formation and goitre size. In addition, while metformin can be beneficial in diabetes mellitus patients, other antidiabetics such as sulfonylureas, pioglitazone, and thiazolidinediones can negatively impact diabetes.³ But in this study, we did not observe significant impact of glycemic control on thyroid hormone levels. Although, insulin treatment alone was significantly associated with thyroid abnormality. But further studies should be done to confirm the evidence.

CONCLUSION

Although the frequency of thyroid function abnormality is less than 20%, but cannot be ignored as it can deteriorate the quality of life of diabetic patients. Thus, we have get evidence for local population and now in future we will implement a practice to screen diabetic patients on regular intervals for thyroid function tests in order to timely detect any changes in thyroid function.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

None.

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